

The Unjournal

Evaluation Summary and Metrics: "Urban Forests: Environmental Health Values and Risks"

Evaluator 1 Evaluator 2 Ben Balmford

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ABSTRACT¹

Understanding the health impacts of tree planting and re-greening is central to understanding the co-benefits and costs of climate and biodiversity-focused policy. The paper "Urban Forests: Environmental Health Values and Risks"^[1] begins to address this question in a context in which the climate and biodiversity benefits may be small compared to the more immediate health effects: the re-greening of a mega city. We organized two evaluations of this paper. The two evaluations both recognise the significance of the work, but diverge in their assessment of the paper's causal identification. Nonetheless, this does not diminish from the paper's important impact implications: urban greening has large positive impacts through substantial reductions in PM2.5 concentrations despite increases in allergic reactions to the increased pollen loads. To read these evaluations, please see the links below.

Evaluations

1. [Evaluator 1](#)
2. [Evaluator 2](#)

Overall ratings

We asked evaluators to provide overall assessments as well as ratings for a range of specific criteria.

I. Overall assessment (See footnote²)

II. Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5): On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' should this be published in?³ *Note: 0= lowest/none, 5= highest/best.*

	Overall assessment (0-100)	Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5)
Evaluator 1	60	2.5
Evaluator 2	90	4.5

See "[Metrics](#)" below for a more detailed breakdown of the evaluators' ratings across several categories. To see these ratings in the context of all Unjournal ratings, with some analysis, see our [data presentation here](#).⁴

See [here](#) for the current full evaluator guidelines, including further explanation of the requested ratings.

Evaluation summaries

Anonymous evaluator 1

The paper tackles a very interesting and relevant question about the environmental and health impact of urban forests i.e how human-led greening of urban areas affects well-being through its impact on pollution and pollen. The paper's strength lies in bringing together several data sources with high spatial resolution and decomposing the policy impact into vegetation density & greenery, air quality and finally health. Moreover the discussion on health and environment trade off is also new and insightful. The main critique is that claims of causality in the paper are not substantiated within the current estimation framework. However, I believe with the excellent data sources available to the authors this can be addressed in the future.

Anonymous evaluator 2

This is an excellent, thorough, and well-written paper on an important topic of urban greenery and health. The methodology builds on well-established methods and is convincing with ample placebo and robustness checks. The authors could further improve policy impact by expanding on the external validity of these findings by describing, exploring, and empirically characterizing the setting and MMP further: what contributes to its success, what greenery is used, and how is the greenery planted?

Metrics

Ratings

[See here](#) for details on the categories below, and the guidance given to evaluators.

	Evaluator 1 Anonymous		Evaluator 2 Anonymous	
Rating category	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*
Overall assessment ⁵	60	(45, 90)	90	(86, 94)
Claims, strength, characterization of evidence ⁶	45	(40, 50)	92	(85, 95)
Advancing knowledge and practice ⁷	67	(60, 70)	88	(82, 94)

Methods: Justification, reasonableness, validity, robustness ⁸	55	(50, 60)	92	(88, 96)
Logic & communication ⁹	51	(50, 55)	92	(87, 95)
Open, collaborative, replicable ¹⁰	50	(45, 60)	88	(84, 92)
Real-world relevance ^{11, 12}	70	(60, 80)	88	(80, 92)
Relevance to global priorities ^{13, 14}	70	(60, 80)	88	(80, 92)

Journal ranking tiers

[See here](#) for more details on these tiers.

	Evaluator 1 Anonymous		Evaluator 2 Anonymous	
Judgment	Ranking tier (0-5)	Comments	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI
On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' <i>should</i> this be published in?	2.5	¹⁵	4.5	(4.3, 4.7)

<p>What 'quality journal' do you expect this work <i>will</i> be published in?</p>	<p>2.5</p>		<p>4.4</p>	<p>(4.2, 4.6)</p>
<p>See here for more details on these tiers.</p>	<p><i>We summarize these as:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.0: Marginally respectable/Little to no value • 1.0: OK/Somewhat valuable • 2.0: Marginal B-journal/Decent field journal • 3.0: Top B-journal/Strong field journal • 4.0: Marginal A-Journal/Top field journal • 5.0: A-journal/Top journal 			

Claim identification and assessment (summary)

For the full discussions, see the corresponding sections in each linked evaluation.

	<p>Main research claim¹⁶</p>	<p>Belief in claim¹⁷</p>
<p>Evaluator 1</p>	<p>1. Document a substantial greening up of Beijing by the MMP programme, specifically NDVI growth to accelerate after 2012, the year of the project implementation</p> <p>2. Quantify the impact of urban forests on downwind air quality improvement using a quasi-experimental research design i.e. increased vegetation growth by MMP reduces average PM2.5 concentration at city population hubs by 4.2 percent and led to a 7.4 percent increase in pollen exposure.</p>	<p>I don't believe these claims are causal as stated by the authors. The estimation framework is not rigorous enough to identify these impacts. Currently, they are correlational evidence.</p>
<p>Evaluator 2</p>	<p>Urban tree planting provides net health benefits by reducing air pollution (4.2%) despite meaningful increases in pollen exposure (7.4%). Overall, the health value of Beijing's Million Mu Project (55 billion CNY over the past decade) will likely exceed its cost (75 billion CNY) in the next decade.</p>	<p>I am quite convinced by the claim as I found the research framework and empirical strategy convincing, with ample robustness and placebo checks (outside vs. inside MMP areas, upwind vs. downwind, etc.).</p>

Evaluation manager's discussion **18**

Understanding the health impacts of tree planting and re-greening is clearly central to understanding the co-benefits and costs of climate and biodiversity focussed policy. This paper begins to address this question in a context in which the climate and biodiversity benefits may be small compared to the more immediate health effects: the re-greening of a mega city.

The two evaluations both recognise the significance of the work, but diverge in their assessment of the paper's causal identification. In part, it seems that this is because of slightly different foci. Evaluation 1 seems to focus on the second half of the paper: "what are the impacts of re-greening?" Meanwhile, Evaluation 2 has more of a focus on the link between the specific programme and the resulting re-greening. Indeed, the strategy to identify the impact of the planting programme (MMP) could be strengthened by, for instance, including wholly untreated sites (e.g. other cities). This approach would help differentiate the effects of the program from those of other policy levers and general trends.

Nonetheless, this does not diminish from the paper's important impact implications: urban regreening has large positive impacts through substantial reductions in PM2.5 concentrations despite increases in allergic reactions to the increased pollen loads

Issues meriting further evaluation

The evaluators generally did a strong job of considering each of the suggested issues raised [in these notes](#), which we shared with them. Still, one point that seems to have been under-addressed is "distributional impacts and inequality—i.e. who wins or loses from urban greening and how that might vary by demographics or geography". ([See LLM-assisted discussion at the bottom of that doc here.](#))

Unjournal process notes

Why we chose this paper [these headings are optional]

From our internal notes:

Air quality in Asian cities has been investigated by several EA funders (OP, founders pledge). I don't know how much they considered urban forests as an intervention, but this paper examines how they benefit local air quality, but also increase risks from pollen exposure.

This paper studies what I think is a really important question: how human-led greening of urban areas affects well-being through its impact on pollution and pollen? This seems a highly policy relevant question, particularly as the world urbanizes and given that a bunch of local governments have the option of making decisions which could affect urban greenery.

These are also ecosystem (dis)services which I don't think have been looked at very much in this context (vs, say, recreation benefits, and to a lesser extent possibly also reductions in flooding).

I also like how they decompose effects: policy -> changes in greenery -> changes in pollutants -> changes in health outcomes (rather than just policy -> changes in health outcomes).

Evaluation process, author engagement

We asked the author team (including early-career researchers) for permission to evaluate this paper, which they granted.¹⁹ This can be seen as a sign of their confidence in their work, truth-seeking mindset, and commitment to open inquiry. They were very responsive and encouraging; we are grateful for this cooperation. They opted not to provide a response to these evaluations, but as always, we welcome a future response.

As noted above, we shared [these notes](#) with the evaluators, with suggestions for potential issues to consider.

References

1. Xing, J., Hu, Z., Xia, F., Xu, J., & Zou, E. (2023, rev. 2024). Urban Forests: Environmental Health Values and Risks. NBER Working Paper No. 31554. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w31554>

Footnotes

1. This abstract draws from the evaluation manager's (Ben Balmford) brief report. [↵](#)
2. We asked them to rank this paper "heuristically" as a percentile "relative to all serious research in the same area that you have encountered in the last three years." We requested they "consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice." [↵](#)
3. See ranking tiers discussed [here](#). [↵](#)
4. Note: if you are reading this before, or soon after this has been publicly released, the ratings from this paper may not yet have been incorporated into that data presentation. [↵](#)
5. Judge the quality of the research heuristically. Consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice. [↵](#)
6. "Do the authors do a good job of (i) stating their main questions and claims, (ii) providing strong evidence and powerful approaches to inform these, and (iii) correctly characterizing the nature of their evidence?"

This was on the newer form only ↵

7.

To what extent does the project contribute to the field or to practice, particularly in ways that are directly or indirectly relevant to global priorities and impactful interventions?

↵

8. Are methods clearly justified and explained? Are methods and their underlying assumptions reasonable? Are the results likely to be robust to changes in the assumptions? Have the authors avoided bias and questionable research practices? ↵

9. Are concepts clearly defined? Is the reasoning transparent? Are conclusions consistent with the evidence (or formal proofs) presented? Are the data and/or analysis, including tables and figures, relevant to the argument? ↵

10.

Would another researcher be able to replicate the analysis? Are the method and its details explained sufficiently? Is the source of the data clear? Is the data made as widely available as possible, with clear labeling and explanation? Do the authors provide resources that are likely to enable future research and meta-analysis?

↵

11.

Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic and relevant to practitioners?

↵

12.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

”Are the paper’s chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?”

“Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?” ↵

13. Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions? [↵](#)

14.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" [↵](#)

15. This is based on the assumption that comments are incorporated. [↵](#)

16.

The evaluator was given the following instructions:

Identify the most important and impactful factual claim this research makes – e.g., a binary claim or a point estimate or prediction.

Please state the authors' claim precisely and quantitatively. Identify the source of the claim (i.e., cite the paper), and briefly mention the evidence underlying this. We encourage you to explain why you believe this claim is important, either here, or in the text of your report. [↵](#)

17. Evaluators were asked: To what extent do you *believe* the claim you stated above? Feel free to express this either a. in terms of the probability of the claim being true, b. as a credible interval for the parameter being estimated, or c. however you feel comfortable. [↵](#)

18. This text was written by Ben Balmford. [↵](#)

19. See a discussion of our policies on this [here](#), [↵](#)

References

1. Xing, J., Hu, Z., Xia, F., Xu, J., & Zou, E. (2023). *Urban Forests: Environmental Health Values and Risks*. National Bureau of Economic Research. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w31554> [↵](#)